

Parent-Adolescent Gender Match in Single-Parent Families: Does it Matter?

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Changes in family structure can disrupt family functioning and place adolescents at heightened psychological risk. The absence of one parent in a single-parent household is often associated with increased emotional and behavioral difficulties during adolescence. The objective of the present study was to compare adolescents from single-parent families with and without parent-adolescent gender match on psychological problems. Using a mixed sampling technique combining purposive and quota sampling techniques, 100 adolescents (50 from single-mother & 50 from single-father families), comprising equal numbers of boys and girls in each type of family were recruited from a district in Kerala. Psychological problems were assessed using a standardized self-report measure. The one-way ANOVA results of the study showed that girls living with single fathers have higher psychological problems compared to girls living with single mothers, boys living with single mothers, and boys living with single fathers. No significant difference in psychological problems was observed between boys living with single mothers and boys living with single fathers. Findings show the importance of considering parent-adolescent gender combinations to get a better understanding of the psychological problems among adolescents in single-parent families. It emphasizes the need for gender-sensitive and context-specific mental health interventions to support adolescents growing up in single-parent families.

Keywords: Adolescents, single mothers, single fathers, parent-adolescent gender, psychological problems

The increasing rates of divorce, separation, migration, unwed biological conception, and parental death have contributed to the change in family structures and led to the emergence of single-parent families. The disruptions in the family structure might be a reason that leads to the psychological vulnerability of adolescents living in these families (Macková, 2022). Single-parent families are those households where either the father or the mother is absent because of reasons such as divorce, marital separation, unwed pregnancy, or the death of a spouse or partner (Greenberg, 2002). About 8% of the global population lives in single-parent families (Bhatt, 2020). In India, the percentage of single-parent families is around 9.5%, where the reasons for single-parenthood are due to death of a spouse, divorce, or separation (Census of India, 2011). In the context of children, about 6.8% of children live in single-parent households globally, with India reporting a figure of approximately to 5% (Kramer, 2019). In Kerala, 25% live with a single parent, mainly their mother (IIPS, 2021).

Literature shows that children from single-parent families are more vulnerable to failing in academics, experiencing sexual abuse and food insecurity (Uma, 2017), depressive and/or anxiety symptoms (Abedini et al., 2017), and low self-esteem (Malik et al.,

2022). Adolescents in single-parent family structures experience higher levels of emotional and behavioral problems (Maurya et al., 2015) and low emotional stability (Lahiri & Verma, 2023). They also show reduced resilience (Devi & Rani, 2023) and poorer academic achievement (Kunjachan et al., 2021) when compared to those in two-parent families. Experiencing the loss of a parent during adolescence can lead to diverse emotional and behavioral challenges, such as feelings of depression, thoughts of suicide, heightened anxiety, sleep disturbances, substance abuse, and difficulties functioning both at school and within the home environment (Farella-Guzzo & Gobbi, 2023). Similarly, adolescents whose parents are separated report higher rates of mental health issues than those whose parents are still together (Karhina et al., 2023).

Although multiple theoretical models have been proposed to explain the elevated risk of adverse outcomes among youth from single-parent families compared to those from two-parent families, considerably less attention has been given to differences between children from single-mother and single-father families. The gender of the custodial parent, single mother or single father, may differentially influence adolescents' psychological outcomes. Two broad theoretical perspectives, essentialist and constructivist models have been advanced to account for these differences (Downey et al., 1998; Dufur et al., 2010). The essentialist view holds onto the fact that both men and women have inborn differences that help to develop their roles as parents, where they follow different methods in parenting children (Dufur et al., 2018). On the other hand, the constructivists focus on the view that the changes or differences in the practices of parenting that men and women take arise from the socially constructed gender role concepts and not from the physiological differences. In a family, mothers are more likely to take the responsibility of nurturing, where they provide more emotional support to the family members, whereas fathers are typically responsible for providing protection and maintaining

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discipline. Both these gender roles complement each other and create a balance in the family. When there is an absence of one parent, it may create changes in the development of children living in this family. Globally, there are 101.3 million single mothers who live alone with their children, and the proportion of single mothers living alone with their children in India accounts for 4.5% or approximately 13 million households across the country (Bhatt, 2020). Single fathers are less common than single mothers, as men are more likely to remarry and handover their children to the care of their mothers or other female members of the family.

The parents' gender, in combination with the child's gender is an important, yet underexplored, factor influencing adolescent adjustment in single-parent families. From a gender socialization perspective, same-gender parents may stand as role models, improving the emotional understanding, communication, and identity development among the children. On the other hand, opposite-gender parents may face difficulties in addressing the gender-specific emotional and developmental needs of the children, especially during adolescence. The gender of the child and parent in a family may have a distinct role in the living experiences of the children. Understanding these dynamics can inform gender-sensitive mental health interventions and family-based support programs that are tailored to the specific needs of adolescents living with same gender or opposite gender single-parents. The present study aimed to examine the differences in psychological problems across parent-adolescent gender combinations among adolescents from single-parent families in Kerala.

Method

Participants

A mixed sampling technique combining purposive and quota sampling techniques was used to select the sample of 50 adolescents from single-mother families (25 boys & 25 girls) aged 13-18 years ($M_{age} = 15.52$; $SD_{age} = 1.47$), 50 adolescents from single-father families (25 boys & 25 girls) aged 13-18 years ($M_{age} = 14.94$; $SD_{age} = 1.52$) from a district in Kerala. The inclusion criteria used include adolescents between 13-18 years of age, of both genders, living with their single mother or father, due to parental separation, divorce, or death. Adolescents with known physical illnesses and those whose single biological parent had remarried or was not residing with them were excluded. The presence or absence of known physical illness of the participants was confirmed by their parents through a statement included in the informed consent form. Participation in this study was entirely voluntary, and only those adolescents who agreed to take part and obtained parental consent were included in the study.

Measure

Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ, Goodman, 1997): The Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire is a brief behavioural screening tool designed to assess emotional and behavioural functioning in children and adolescents. The instrument consists of 25 items, which are organized into five subscales: emotional difficulties, peer difficulties, conduct difficulties, hyperactivity, and prosocial behaviour. Each subscale includes five items. Participants indicate how well each statement applies to them on a 3-point rating scale: 0 (*not true*) to 2 (*certainly true*). For the present study, the first four subscales were combined to produce a total difficulties score,

representing psychological problems in the present study. The higher scores on the scale indicate greater psychological problems. For the present study, the SDQ was administered in bilingual format, with each item presented in both English and Malayalam. The Malayalam items used were the previously translated and validated Malayalam version of SDQ (Owen et al., 2015). In the present study, the Cronbach's alpha for the psychological problems dimension of the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire for adolescents from single-mother and single-father families was .86 and .90 respectively.

Procedure

Prior to the data collection, written or oral permission was obtained from the school authorities after providing a detailed explanation of the study's objectives, scope and procedures. As the participants were minors, written parental consent and participant assent were secured before administering the standardized self-reported measure. Information regarding the purpose of the study, voluntary nature of participation, and the expectations of participation was clearly communicated through informed consent form. Data collection was carried out on school premises during regular instruction hours in a manner that did not interfere with academic activities. Only those students who provided both assent and parental consent, meeting the inclusion criteria of the study were included in the sample.

Ethical Considerations

The ethical considerations of American Psychological Association (APA) relating to the safeguarding of participants and their dignity are strictly followed in the present study. As an initial process, ethical clearance from the Human Research Ethics Committee of Bharathiar University (BUHEC/96/2024) was obtained. Along with this, written or oral consent was collected from the school authorities in order to conduct the study within their schools. After explaining the study's nature and purpose and procedures involved, and also their rights to refuse participation or withdraw from the study without facing any negative consequences at any point in the study, written informed consent was collected from the participant's parents and assent was obtained from the participants. The participants were assured that their personal information would be maintained confidentially.

Results

One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to analyze the data to compare the differences in psychological problems among adolescents living in single-parent families across four distinct groups, i.e., girls living with single mothers, boys living with single mothers, girls living with single fathers, and boys living with single fathers.

Table 1 shows the results of one-way ANOVA and it revealed a significant effect of parent-adolescent gender combinations on psychological problems, $F(3, 96) = 6.48, p < .001$. Post-hoc Tukey HSD analysis indicated that girls living with their single fathers ($M=22.20, SD=8.82$) reported significantly higher psychological problems compared to girls living with single mothers ($M=14.12, SD=7.99$), boys living with single mothers ($M=13.96, SD=7.77$), and boys living with single fathers ($M=13.92, SD=7.58$). No significant differences were observed between boys living with single mothers and single fathers in psychological problems.

Table 1
One-Way ANOVA of Psychological Problems across Parent-Adolescent Gender Combinations in Single-Parent Families

Variable	Group	N	Mean	SD	F
Psychological problems	Girls living with single mother	25	14.12	7.99	6.48***
	Boys living with single mother	25	13.96	7.77	
	Girls living with single father	25	22.20	8.82	
	Boys living with single father	25	13.92	7.58	

Note. *** $p < .001$

Discussion

The present study examined psychological problems among adolescents from single-parent families with a specific focus on parent-adolescent gender match. The findings indicate that girls living with single fathers report significantly higher levels of psychological problems compared to girls living with single mothers, boys living with single mothers, and boys living with single fathers. No significant difference in psychological problems was observed between boys living with single mothers and boys living with single fathers.

Gender of the single-parent has been associated with the development challenges faced by adolescents (Sahib & Aldoori, 2025). Research has shown that adolescents residing with single fathers may be at increased risk for adjustment difficulties across health and psychosocial domains (Ulveseter et al., 2010). Being a girl is also identified as a significant risk for the development of mental health problems such as depression (Cen et al., 2025). In support with the study of the present study, literature shows that girls living with single fathers report higher levels of loneliness and sadness compared to girls living with single mothers and boys living with either parent (Dufur & Woo, 2023). Similarly, research indicates that adolescents in gender-matched families (mother-daughter and father-son) exhibited more adaptive social and emotional adjustment than those in gender-mismatched families, particularly father-daughter dyads (Chen et al., 2025). Girls raised by single fathers exhibit higher masculine traits and experience differential social adjustment compared to their counterparts in single-mother families (Chen et al., 2019). Girls raised by single fathers are also less adjusted to life (Santrock & Warshak, 1979). Girls raised by single-fathers also exhibit higher levels of aggression and behavioral problems, lower levels of self-esteem (Camara & Resnick, 1989), and antisocial behavior than boys raised by single-fathers (Peterson & Zill, 1986). These may contribute to the elevated psychological problems among girls raised by single fathers. A study conducted among young adults in single-parent families, it showed that girls experience emotional distance and role reversal after their mother left during adolescence, forcing them to assume adult responsibilities prematurely. Even though the girls have better achievement in academics, the absence of a maternal role model during their adolescent period contributed to the difficulties with femininity, low self-esteem, and unstable relationships, resulting in long-term psychological vulnerability (Teleoacá, 2025).

The gender socialization view emphasize that the same parent-child gender combination helps improve emotional communication, and share coping mechanisms which can improve the psychological adjustments for the adolescents in their developmental periods.

Mothers with daughters may understand the emotional needs and socialization experiences of the daughters, enabling effective communication on emotional and interpersonal difficulties. Conversely, in parent-adolescent gender-mismatched combinations such as father-daughter families, lack of communication and emotional socialization may emerge, potentially limiting girls to express and regulate their distress effectively. The parental child-rearing gender-role attitudes serve as a mechanism through which parents' own adjustment influences adolescents' social and emotional outcomes, indicating that the transmission of adjustment is shaped by gendered parenting practices rather than parent gender alone (Chen et al., 2025). In the absence of a mother, girls living with single fathers may face challenges in navigating gender-specific developmental tasks such as menstruation (Kalman, 2003), hormonal changes, and difficulty in expressing their emotions.

The findings in the present study also show that boys living with single mothers and single fathers did not differ significantly in psychological problems, indicating that boys may be adaptable to the changes in gender roles in single-parent families. The findings of the present study are supported by previous research suggesting that the internalizing and externalizing problems of the child in divorced families do not differ based on whether they live with same-gender or opposite-gender parent, or share time equally with both parents (Faust et al., 2017). Single fathers experience economic pressure and have lower coping strategies (Hamaedi & Rizkillah, 2024). Single mothers show maladaptive reactions to challenges, face lack of support from family (Deepak & Annalakshmi, 2022), financial problems (Deepak & Annalakshmi, 2022; Johnson & Wu, 2002; Rathi & Pachauri, 2018; Stack & Meredith, 2017) and face mother-adolescent conflicts, along with minimal parental supervision and reduced mother-adolescent engagement (Demo & Acock, 1996). These stressors may show comparable effects on boys across single-mother and single-father families. Thus, despite the differences like stressors experienced by the single mother or father, the psychological problems among the boys may be shaped by general single-parent family stress rather than by the gender of the parent with whom they live.

Conclusion

The present study examined the psychological problems among adolescents from single-parent families with a specific focus on parent-adolescent gender match. The findings demonstrated that girls living with single fathers were more vulnerable to psychological problems compared to girls living with single mothers, boys living with single mothers, and single fathers. In contrast, psychological problems among boys did not vary significantly by parent gender, suggesting that the impact of parent-

adolescent gender dynamics may be more pronounced for girls than for boys. The finding that the parent-adolescent gender mismatch is associated with increased psychological problems in adolescents, particularly in single father-daughter combination highlights the relevance of gendered socialization process. The study contributes to the existing literature emphasizing that the adolescent mental health outcomes in single-parent families are not uniform and differ with parent-adolescent gender combinations. Schools and community mental health services should also be more attentive to the heightened vulnerability of girls living with single fathers and provide early screening and targeted psychosocial support.

Implications and Limitations of the Study

The findings of the present study have both practical and research implications. The study emphasizes that the psychological problems among adolescents from single-parent families vary based on the parent-adolescent gender combinations, in which father-daughter gender combination shows the greatest vulnerability. This highlights the importance of considering the gender of both parent and child in a single-parent family, thereby informing the mental health professionals and the policy makers to develop specific interventions and policies that are embedded in the gender specific contexts. This can enhance the living conditions of adolescents in single-parent families. However, the study has a few limitations that have to be addressed while interpreting the results. The sample for the present study was drawn from a single district in Kerala, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to a wider population. Further, the study adopted a cross-sectional research design, and future studies with a longitudinal or mixed methods approach can give more detailed information regarding the risk and protective factors for mental health among adolescents from single-mother and single-father families, beyond the concept of parent-adolescent gender combinations.

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